

CONCEPT-BASED EXPLANATIONS FOR MUSIC EMOTION RECOGNITION

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ABSTRACT

Concept-based explanations have been shown to be useful in other domains and recently found their way into music information retrieval research. The idea is to provide the user with human-understandable, high-level concepts as an explanation for a model’s prediction. There are two ways of obtaining concept-based explanations for an existing model (post-hoc): one requires additional training data labeled with the concepts of interest, the other extracts concepts without requiring prior knowledge, which is generally advantageous; however, it suffers from the problem that we do not know the meaning of the discovered concepts and require users to label them. In this work, we study this problem in the context of music emotion recognition. We conduct a listening experiment which shows that extracted concepts satisfy desired properties: *coherence* and *meaningfulness*; demonstrate how concepts can be presented to users, and explore the possibility of automatically labeling concepts without requiring users. In addition, we show quantitatively that the concepts are also faithful to the model.

1. INTRODUCTION

Many different methods for obtaining explanations have been applied to models in MIR: Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations (LIME) [1] are the basis for different adaptations to the audio domain [2–4]. LIME-based explanations are applied after the model has been trained (*post-hoc*). Some approaches attempt to make the model *intrinsically* interpretable, e.g., by introducing an intermediate interpretable layer [3,5,6], using prototypes [7], flow-based invertible models [8], attention [9,10], or by combining prototypes and attention [11].

Another promising type of explanations has been proposed: concept-based explanations, which were first introduced by Kim et al. [12] (named TCAV). Their approach requires the user to provide additional samples which are labeled with the desired concepts (*supervised*). One follow-up work by Zhang et al. [13] introduces Non-negative Concept Activation Vectors (NCAVs) based on Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) of the activation space providing unlabeled concepts (*unsupervised*).

Concept-based explanations have also been used for gaining a better understanding about models in MIR [14, 15].

Foscarin et al. [14] have demonstrated both supervised (TCAV [12]) and unsupervised (NCAV [13]) concept extraction techniques on a composer classification system. The supervised approach has some drawbacks: One has to reason about possibly relevant concepts, and collect or record data that represents this concept in advance. There are also disadvantages with the unsupervised approach: The number of CAVs has to be specified, and a domain expert has to label the extracted concepts; the latter poses some additional difficulties: it is unclear whether examples of a concept are *coherent* (i.e., perceptually similar) and *meaningful* (i.e., whether human listeners will agree on the naming), both of which are desired properties for concept-based explanations [16].

The goal of this paper is to address drawbacks of the unsupervised concept extraction approach and to gain more insights into learned concepts. This will get us closer to providing users with high-level, human-understandable explanations. We will study this in the context of a specific MIR task – music emotion recognition (MER) from audio, using a dataset that in addition to raw audio also provides a large set of audio features.

Our contributions are the following: We propose a simple way to select a useful number of concepts per layer. We conduct a listening experiment which shows that the extracted concepts are *coherent* and *meaningful* (desiderata mentioned by Ghorbani et al. [16]) and present quantitative results implying that the explanatory concepts also exhibit high *fidelity*. We introduce a prototypical user interface to demonstrate how a concept can be presented to users, e.g., model developers. Finally, we explore the possibility to automatically label concepts by using the provided audio features and demonstrate – for one automatically labeled CAV – that it reacts to changes in the input as expected.¹

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 introduces Non-negative Concept Activation Vectors. In Section 3 we describe our MER model. Our approach for explaining music emotion is outlined in Section 4. The listening experiment and the resulting findings are described in Sections 5. The prototypical user interface is described in Section 6. An approach for automatically labeling concepts is explored in Section 7. We conclude in Section 8.

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¹ All code and other materials for reproducing our experiments are available online: https://github.com/expectopatronum/concepts_mer_smc2025

2. NON-NEGATIVE CONCEPT ACTIVATION VECTORS

The basic idea underlying concept-based explanations is to provide humans with high-level explanations in possibly abstract terms. To that end, we need to extract *Concept Activation Vectors (CAVs)* which represent “concepts” in the space of a layer’s activations [12] that might capture such higher-level ideas, e.g., “instrumentation”, “beat”, “vocal style”, etc. In the following, we describe how CAVs are extracted and several metrics that can be computed based on these.

2.1 Extracting Concepts

Our explainer is based on work by Zhang et al [13] and Kim et al [12]. The prediction $Y = m(X)$ for a trained convolutional model m and input audios X can be split into two parts at any layer l : $Y = m(X) = g_l(f_l(X))$. $f_l(X)$ computes activations $A_l \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times H \times W \times C}$, where B is the number of samples in the batch, H and W are the height and width of the activation map, and C is the number of channels. $g_l(A_l)$ then computes Y (i.e., g_l represents the part of the network ‘above’ layer l) (depicted in Figure 1). To obtain Concept Activation Vectors (CAVs) for a layer l of interest, we first compute activations A_l , flatten these to $A'_l \in \mathbb{R}^{(B \cdot H \cdot W) \times C}$ and train an NMF [18] model on these². NMF is applicable to non-negative matrices and approximates these by two non-negative matrices, which we will call $S_l \in \mathbb{R}^{(B \cdot H \cdot W) \times C'}$ (the concept scores) and $N_l \in \mathbb{R}^{C' \times C}$ (the CAVs): $A'_l \approx S_l N_l$.

The optimization objective, using the Frobenius norm, for this decomposition is the following (omitting l for simplicity):

$$\min_{S, N} \|A' - SN\|_F \quad (1)$$

$$\text{such that } S \geq 0, N \geq 0.$$

2.2 Average Concept Presence

Averaging over the h - and w -dimension of $S' \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times H \times W \times C'}$ (reshaped version of S), gives us the average concept presence (ACP) for each example b and concept k :

$$\text{ACP}_{b,k} = \frac{1}{H \times W} \sum_h \sum_w S'_{b,h,w,k} \quad (2)$$

This score was first mentioned by Zhang et al. [13] and termed “Average Concept Presence” by Foscari et al. [14]. We will use this score to rank examples for each concept.

2.3 Local and Global Explanations

To measure how relevant a concept k in layer l (n_k^l denotes the corresponding CAV) is for predicting a certain class q for a single input example (*local* explanation), we can use the *conceptual sensitivity* $\text{SENS}_{k,l,q}$ [12].

Let $f_l(x)$ denote the activations of input x at layer l , $g_{l,q}(f_l(x))$ be the logit for the q th class using activations from layer l , and n_k^l represent the Concept Activation Vector (CAV) for concept k in layer l . Then the conceptual sensitivity is computed as follows:

$$\text{SENS}_{k,l,q}(x) = \nabla g_{l,q}(f_l(x)) \cdot n_k^l$$

To obtain a *global* explanation, i.e., to answer the question which concept is relevant for predicting a certain class in general, we can compute *CAV scores*: we take a set of examples belonging to the class of interest and compute the ratio of examples with positive conceptual sensitivity [12].

2.4 Fidelity

Fidelity has been introduced as an explanation objective by Ribeiro et al. [1] and signifies the requirement that the explainer is faithful to the model that we want to explain. The exact definition varies depending on the nature of the explainer. We define fidelity as the number of class predictions that do not change when feeding the reconstructed activations through the network.

3. PREDICTING MUSIC EMOTION

In this section we describe the dataset, the model architecture and the training setup for training a model that classifies input audios into a set of discrete emotion classes.

3.1 4Q Audio Emotion Dataset

Panda et al. [17, 19] published the “4Q Audio Emotion Dataset” with a wide variety of standard and novel audio features for MER. It contains audio snippets and 1714 audio features for 900 music pieces covering a broad set of musical styles³, each annotated into one of the four quadrants of Russell’s [20] valence-arousal space (225 audio samples per quadrant). These quadrants (see the upper right part of Figure 1) are generally equated with four basic emotions; happiness/exuberance (Q1); anxiety (Q2); depression (Q3); and contentment (Q4).⁴ The four quadrant labels serve as discrete target classes for our emotion recognition model.

The 1714 features consist of 898 ‘standard’ descriptors (e.g., zero crossing rate, low energy rate, etc.) computed using different toolboxes and 816 ‘novel’ features (including but not limited to melodic, rhythmic, musical texture and expressivity features). We refer the interested reader to [17, 19] for more details. This dataset serves two purposes: (1) the audio is used to train our fully convolutional MER model, (2) the set of provided audio features will be used to label our extracted concepts.

³ The metadata includes genre tags (sorted by decreasing frequency): Pop/Rock, Jazz, Electronic, International, R&B, Vocal, Country, Blues, Rap, Latin, Folk, Reggae, New Age, Stage & Screen, Easy Listening, Avant-Garde, Comedy/Spoken, Holiday, Religious, Classical, Children’s.

⁴ Russell himself [20] refers to the quadrants as ‘affect concepts’ and names them excitement, distress, depression, and contentment.

² We used <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.decomposition.NMF.html> with default parameters.

Figure 1: The upper part schematically shows the architecture for *predicting emotion*. The upper right part shows emotion quadrants in valence-arousal space, with indicative positioning of various emotion words (based on [17]). The lower part shows how concepts of an arbitrary layer l are *extracted* and *labeled by humans* to later *explain* the emotion predictions.

3.2 Music Emotion Recognition Model

For training an end-to-end MER model, we base our implementation on a fully convolutional NN (FCN) [21,22]. Our model consists of 5 convolutional layers (with 32, 64, 64, 64 and 32 channels), each followed by BatchNorm [23], a ReLU [24] and max pooling. The convolutional layers are followed by a linear layer, Dropout ($p=0.5$) and a Softmax layer. This architecture can take full-length audio input (30 seconds in our experiments) which is useful since the audio features we are comparing to (see Section 3.1) are computed on the full audio.

We performed grid search to determine the optimal hyperparameters. The highest validation accuracy was achieved on a model trained for 100 epochs using Adam [25] with a learning rate of $5 * 10^{-4}$ and a batch size of 8. We retrained the best model 10 times and report the performance on the test set in terms of accuracy: 0.734 ± 0.014 . An SVM trained and evaluated on the same train and test set, using the hyperparameters provided by Panda et al. [17], achieves an accuracy of 0.769. The CNN trained on the spectrograms does not match the performance of the SVM trained on the hand-crafted features. Due to the small size of the data set, this is not unexpected and similar results have been reported before [26].

4. EXPLAINING MUSIC EMOTION

In this section we first describe the desired properties we expect from our explanations; secondly, we outline the details of computing the Concept Activation Vectors (CAVs); and, finally, we describe our proposed methods for choosing an appropriate number of CAVs per layer, and for labeling these concepts by associating them with features.

4.1 Desiderata

Recent explainability literature comes with a long list of desired properties such as coherence, meaningfulness, and importance [16], interpretability and fidelity [1, 13]. For this work we will focus on coherence, meaningfulness, and fidelity⁵. We stipulate that concepts used for explaining models in MIR should be:

- *coherent*: examples of a concept are expected to be perceptually similar to each other, and different from other examples [16];
- *meaningful*: different humans should assign similar meanings to examples of the same concept [16];
- *faithful*: an explainer is faithful [1] if it behaves similar to the model being explained; for NCAVs this means that predictions using reconstructed activations should be close to the original prediction.

4.2 Extracting Musical Concepts

To gain insights into what the model has learned we use the approach outlined in Section 2. As opposed to other publications who focus on the penultimate layer [13, 14], we compute CAVs for each of the 5 convolutional layers. For computing CAVs we have to decide which data to use for training the NMF (“auxiliary data”).

Ramaswamy et al. [27] perform an in-depth analysis of different factors in concept-based explanations, including the choice of the *auxiliary dataset* (sometimes also called “probe dataset”). Their experiments show that the choice of the dataset has a profound impact on the explanations.

⁵ Concept-based explanations are more interpretable than other types of explanations by design [12].

The authors conclude that explanations should only be created for examples that come from the same distribution as the auxiliary data. We follow this suggestion and use our model’s training data for training the explainer, and the unseen test data for all subsequent experiments.

4.3 Number of Concepts per Layer

The algorithm outlined in Section 2.1 decomposes each layer’s activations A' into concept scores S and CAVs N . The number of CAVs C' has to be specified by the user.

To automatically determine an appropriate number of concepts in each layer of the network, we start from the premise that any pair of two CAVs should not be too strongly correlated, to avoid redundancy. For a given layer, we start from some maximum number C' (in our experiments, $C' = 10$) and compute the ACP (see Section 2.2) for each CAV. As long as there are two CAVs with a Spearman’s rank correlation [28] between their ACPs of ≥ 0.9 , we recompute the CAVs using $C' = C' - 1$.

In our case, we ended up with 4 CAVs for layer 1, 6 for layer 2, 10 for layer 3, 10 for layer 4, and 10 for layer 5, respectively.

4.4 Fidelity

As a quantitative metric for the extracted concepts we report the *fidelity* [1, 13]. Averaging the fidelity score for the explainers over 5 different models per layer, we obtain the following values: 0.72 ± 0.05 (layer1), 0.56 ± 0.10 (layer2), 0.87 ± 0.05 (layer3), 0.82 ± 0.09 (layer4), and 0.99 ± 0.01 (layer5). The explainers seem to be relatively faithful for layers 1, 3, 4, and almost perfect for layer 5. We conclude that we should be more careful when looking at explanations for layer 2 than for the other layers, but in general we recommend to look at faithfulness for examples separately when looking at local explanations.

5. LISTENING EXPERIMENT

We designed a listening experiment to investigate whether the extracted concepts are *coherent* and *meaningful* (see Section 4.1). Regarding *coherence*, we draw inspiration from recent work who have conducted *intruder detection* experiments [16, 29], inspired by [30]. Participants are presented with a set of examples, where all except one belong to the same concept. They are asked to identify the one that does not (termed *intruder*). To test *meaningfulness* we ask the participants about the similarities among the non-intruders.

Participants are presented with 10 sets (2 per layer) of 4 audio examples each. Each set consists of the 3 audio examples with the highest ACP for a concept of interest, and one intruder (which has the lowest ACP for the selected concept). We take a 10 second snippet (which has the highest/lowest ACP for this piece) for each audio example. For each set we ask:

QU1: Which of the following pieces of music is different from the other three pieces?

Figure 2: This figure shows the intruder detection rate for each of the 10 items in the questionnaire labeled by the corresponding layer and CAV.

QU2: How confident are you that the piece you selected is different from the others? [Four checkboxes ranging from “I am very confident” to “I had to guess”.]

QU3: Please describe the common characteristics shared by the three similar pieces. What makes these three pieces similar to each other?

To reduce the variability among the participants, we asked people between 25 and 35 years who have learned to play at least one instrument to participate. In order to not bias the participants’ answers they were not aware that the prediction task was music emotion. We used the tool SosciSurvey [31] to create the online questionnaire. Results and findings of the listening experiment are discussed below.

In the following, “item” refers to a set consisting of 4 audios (in total 40 seconds of audio) and the corresponding 3 questions.

5.1 Overall Statistics

We recruited 13 participants. While we have to be careful with drawing conclusions from this small number, it allows us to do a qualitative analysis by asking and analyzing free text questions. The median time spent by a participant for evaluating all 10 items ($10 \times 4 \times 10$ seconds = 6.67 minutes of audio) was 22.15 minutes (IQR = 14.85, 27.5). One participant spent 7.85 minutes in total, with an average time of 47.1 seconds (± 20.3) per item, which means they can not have listened to all audio snippets and thoroughly answered the questions. This participant only identified 50% of the intruders correctly.

5.2 Extracted Concepts are Coherent

Participants correctly identified 76.15% (± 21.89) of the intruders (ranging from 30.77% to 100% per set). The intruder detection rate per concept is visualized in Figure 2. The participants were also asked to state their confidence level, the results are summarized in Table 1. The listeners were very confident about their correct choices, and selected “I had to guess.” more often when they selected a wrong sample as the intruder. These results let us conclude that most of the concepts that we presented to our

	Confidence Level			
	1	2	3	4
incorrect	9	8	8	5
correct	5	9	30	55

Table 1: Reported confidence scores for correctly and incorrectly detected intruders. The confidence scores range from 1 (“I had to guess”) to 4 (“I am very confident.”).

Figure 3: Word clouds summarising the descriptions that participants gave for Layer4/CAV8 (left): all terms center around the notion of ‘genre’, and Layer4/CAV9 (right): no clear semantic focus can be identified.

participants are *coherent*, meaning that examples belonging to the concept are perceptually similar to each other while they are different from other examples [16].

5.3 Extracted Concepts are Meaningful

To evaluate whether the extracted concepts are *meaningful* we look into the participants answers to QU3. Participants were permitted to write anything they wanted, which led to diverse answers with respect to structure (whole sentences vs. lists of terms), length, and content.

We now take a closer look at all answers given for two of the items, one for which all participants detected the correct intruder (`layer4_8`), and the most difficult one - with only 30.77% correct answers (`layer4_9`). For both items we (manually) extracted terms that were used to describe what the participant thought were the three similar audio snippets. The extracted terms for both items are visualized in Figure 3.

The answers for case (a) (where the concept was clearly grasped, with 100% agreement on the intruder) have a clear musical meaning, essentially centering around the notion of genre. This resonates with observations by Eerola [32] on the importance of genre for emotion prediction and suggests that genre should generally be considered for naming concepts in this context. For case (b), no semantic focus is to be expected, as the intruder identification accuracy of the participants was barely above the baseline.

5.4 CAV Scores Relate To Meaningful Features

Table 2 reports the aggregated CAV scores for layer1 (see Section 2). Let us focus on the concepts that were part of the listening experiment (CAV0, CAV2), since we have human annotations for these. CAV0, which has high CAV scores for emotion classes Q1 (0.57) and particularly Q2 (0.70), is described as “energetic”, “fast-paced”, “loud”, and aspects like “aggressive vocals”, “vocal style”, “guitar with distortion”, and “drums” are highlighted. CAV2,

Q	CAV0	CAV1	CAV2	CAV3
Q1	+	o	+	o
Q2	+	+	o	+
Q3	o	o	o	o
Q4	o	o	o	o

Table 2: Abstracted CAV Scores for layer1. Scores $\geq .5$ appear as ‘+’, values < 0.5 as ‘o’.

Presenting Learned Concepts

Figure 4: Top part of the prototypical user interface for presenting learned concepts to users. Descriptions that could be useful for users have been omitted to save space.

which has a high score for Q1 (0.77), is described as “harmonic”, “melodic”, “romantic”, and participants mentioned aspects like “melodic singing” and “singing is clean and happy”. These concept characterizations (indirectly obtained via our listening study) are intuitively compatible with the emotions that the respective emotion quadrants represent (Q1 is generally associated with “happy” and “excited”, Q2 with emotions such as “tense”, “angry”, “distressed”).

6. PRESENTING LEARNED CONCEPTS TO USERS

In this section we are going to demonstrate how the extracted concepts can be presented to potential users, e.g., model developers, musicologists, music producers, or listeners. Although we can compute local (per example) explanations as well (outlined in Section 2.3), similar to previous work [12, 14] we are going to focus on globally analyzing the model, namely by showing what the learned concepts represent. For this purpose we implemented a prototypical user interface (a part of it is shown in Figure 4). A user can select a trained model and a

	layer1 (1)	layer2 (0)	layer3 (6)	layer4 (7)
x	1.00	0.99	0.97	0.78
x_{noise}	0.05	0.08	-0.02	0.00

Table 3: ACP for a test example (x) and an example containing random noise (x_{noise}). The ACP values for the whole test set have been normalized to the range $[0, 1]$. Using the same scaling for new examples can lead to values outside that range.

model layer for analysis. CAV scores can be displayed raw or abstracted (as shown in Table 2). Using this table, we can determine the importance of each CAV for each emotion quadrant (see Section 5.4 for an example). Then the user can select which of the CAVs in this layer they want to look at. If human annotations are available, they will be displayed for the selected CAV. For the purpose of this demo, user descriptions are created with the help of ChatGPT⁶ (<https://openai.com/blog/chatgpt>) using GPT-4o [34]: To this end we copied all descriptions provided by participants of the listening test into one message, each set proceeded by ‘Set01:’, ..., ‘Set10:’ to make them identifiable. We asked ChatGPT “Can you write a short summary for each set, focusing on similarities, and only providing key words?”. ChatGPT provided short summaries for each of the sets, that are used as descriptions. After that (not shown in the screenshot), audio examples for the 3 examples exhibiting the highest concept presence (measured by the ACP score), and one contrastive example (the one with the lowest ACP score, the *intruder* in the listening experiment) are displayed.

7. TOWARDS AUTOMATICALLY LABELING CONCEPTS

Without human labeling, the extracted concepts do not have any meaning. Manually labeling them can become time-consuming when extracting several concepts for all layers. In order to test whether we can automatically label the extracted concepts that explain the high-level emotion predictions and get the most relevant naming, we propose using low- and mid-level descriptors. Features used for audio classification can be divided into different levels, with low-level audio features (e.g., pitch, intensity, ...), mid-level perceptual properties (e.g., articulation, rhythmic stability, melodiousness, ...) [35] and high-level semantic aspects (e.g., genre, emotion) [36]. Low- and mid-level features are also known to be relevant for emotion prediction [17, 19, 35]. Lower-level features can be extracted using toolboxes or standard algorithms; higher-level, more abstract features, could be extracted using models trained to predict the desired quality [5, 22, 37]. In our case, the used dataset comes with precomputed low- and mid-level features (see Section 3.1), therefore we are going to use this as a first attempt to label the concepts.

To label the extracted concepts we compute the Spearman

⁶ Although used for a different purpose, using ChatGPT in this context is inspired by the work presented by Flexer [33].

rank correlation [28] over all test pieces in our dataset, between the ACP (see Section 2.2) and the feature value for all of the provided low- and mid-level features. The assumption is that high values for ACP should correlate with high values for relevant low- and mid-level features. From the obtained ranking, we could use the top- k features, or all features exceeding a certain threshold. For now we will focus on the top- k features, and leave the determination of a proper threshold for future work.

As an example, the following are the top 3 features (and our interpretations) for the first two CAVs: layer1/CAV0: “FFT Spectrum - Average Power Spectrum (median)”, “Roughness (std)”, “Average Specific Loudness Pattern (min)” which seem related to the concept of *Loudness*; and layer1/CAV1: “SCF_12 (mean)”, SCF_11 (mean), and SCF_15 (mean) which are all related to the *Spectral Crest Factor (SCF)*, which measures the peakiness of a spectrum and is expected to be high for tone-like sounds and low for noise [38].

As a simple test whether a CAV reacts to changes the way we would expect it to, we look at four different CAVs (layer1: CAV1, layer2: CAV0, layer3: CAV6, and layer4: 7) which have all been labeled with SCF. We take the test example that has the highest ACP for this concept in layer 1 (x), and generate an example x_{noise} consisting of random white noise with the same mean and standard deviation as x as a counterexample. We calculate the ACP for both examples (reported in Table 3). We can see that the values are high for x across all layers and close to 0 for x_{noise} . This indicates that the concept actually represents something like SCF. While, due to high correlation between audio features [17], this CAV may not only represent SCF, the feature can serve as a label.

8. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we explored unsupervised concept-based explanations for a deep music emotion recognition model. The unsupervised approach is more suitable when potential concepts are not known, or auxiliary data that represents those concepts is not available. We conducted a listening experiment that showed that the extracted concepts are *coherent* and *meaningful*. Quantitative experiments showed that the extracted concepts are *faithful*. We created a prototypical user interface to demonstrate how concepts can be represented to users. Furthermore, we investigated an approach for automatically labeling extracted concepts.

There is still room for future work. While we can automatically assign low- and mid-level meaning to the concepts, the listening experiment has shown that this is not what humans use to describe cohesive examples - concept-based explanations in MIR might require multiple levels of labels assigned to each concept; and we might have to incorporate automatic music tagging models [22, 39] that can provide richer labels for giving meaning to the concepts.

Another interesting line of research could be investigating whether different layers in the network learn, or represent, different levels of features, as it has been discovered for deep scene recognition networks (in the image domain) [40].

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